

CONCEPT AND PROCEDURE OF THE CONTENT ANALYSIS METHOD FOR EXPLORING INFORMATION IN THE FIELDS OF ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION, COMMUNICATION, SOCIAL SCIENCES, AND HUMANITIES

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Abstract

Content analysis is one of the important research methods in the dissemination of information and scientific innovation in the rapid development of the current and future information, communication and technology. This method is used in qualitative and quantitative research. The goal is to explore and uncover the meaning behind information in various written, oral, and digital media as well as multi-visual and multi-lingual. This method can be used to conduct studies in various disciplines, such as education, communication, religion, social, humanities and political science as well as other fields. This article comprehensively discusses the concept, objectives, urgency, and procedures related to the implementation of content analysis, accompanied by an illustration of its application with examples conducted in research in the field of Islamic Religious Education. The discussion of this article is carried out using literature review techniques. Data collection and analysis include editing, organizing and finding references that are analyzed as research data, using the flow of library review analysis. The description of research results related to content analysis is expected to provide an understanding of the concept, objectives and urgency as well as the procedure for applying the type of content analysis research method. In addition, it is expected to encourage researchers to conduct research in the field of Islamic Religious Education and various other scientific fields with content analysis.

Keywords: *Content Analysis; Text; Meaning; Pattern; Unit; Category; Islamic Religious Education Communication*

INTRODUCTION

International labor migration is a global phenomenon that is inseparable from the dynamics of The rapid and widespread development of information today requires strategic efforts to consume and produce it as media and information that function in daily life, both in conventional and digital forms. Media serves as a tool for accessing, analyzing, evaluating, and creating messages across various contexts. Various communication media play a central role in disseminating messages and information widely to all levels of society in this era of digital advancement, where information proliferation has become an unavoidable phenomenon. This phenomenon has become a crucial factor in understanding and systematically and objectively analyzing the content behind the unlimited flow of information.

Based on this urgency, various research methods have emerged as tools to explore and uncover the content or meaning behind information in media, one of which is the content analysis method. The use of content analysis enables researchers to examine messages contained in various types of media effectively. This method has become highly important in communication studies as well as in the social sciences, as analytical skills can systematically reveal patterns, themes, and relationships hidden within messages to provide functional meaning. Thus, the purpose of using content analysis as a research method is to improve the quality of deducing meaning by connecting

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categories with the context or environment that produces the data or information. In essence, content analysis offers a deep understanding of the relationship between dynamics and phenomena occurring in society (Rozali, Yuli, 2022). With the dynamics of the digital era, characterized by media centralization, changes in information usage patterns, and algorithm dominance, contemporary media has become increasingly complex and diverse. Society can access information through various channels such as social media, online news portals, and streaming platforms, leading to fragmented attention and content overload. In this context, content analysis emerges as a relevant methodological approach to examine meaning, patterns, and representations in various forms of communication, including text, images, and videos. Content analysis allows researchers to identify issue framing, media bias, and the dynamics of public discourse hidden behind content presentation (Ulfah *et al.*, 2022).

Content analysis is one of the most important analytical methods for extracting and evaluating textual meaning systematically in fields such as Islamic education, communication, and da'wah, with the aim of understanding and optimizing the delivery of religious messages to make them more effective and impactful, as well as in the fields of language, literature, social, and political sciences (Huda *et al.*, 2013; Sumarno, 2020). Focusing on research in Islamic Religious Education, which is a crucial field in education, content analysis can be used to examine various aspects, such as the analysis of educational materials, the feasibility of textbooks, instructional materials, and the suitability of media, methods, as well as learning evaluation (Azhari, 2021).

Content analysis is also used to extract the meaning of messages in Islamic da'wah and communication, both formal and informal, written and digital, through media such as films, YouTube, TikTok, and other social platforms (Arafat Yasser Gusti, 2018). Therefore, this analysis is important as an alternative research method using document-based or literature-based data. In addition, the flexibility of content analysis allows it to be applied both quantitatively and qualitatively (Sumarno, 2020). Although, according to Berelson as cited in (Ulfah *et al.*, 2022), content analysis is oriented as a qualitative research method, in practice it is used to determine the characteristics of documents or to compare them. Researchers using this method not only have the ability to present existing data but can also substantially minimize subjective bias. This ensures that research results using content analysis become more valid, scientifically accountable, and remain relevant to current conditions.

Furthermore, this method can be used to explore meaning in media and content such as Islamic educational materials on social media and other digital platforms. For example, a study analyzing a Qur'anic study program broadcast on YouTube TVUPI Digital using a qualitative content analysis approach aims to understand the content, delivery style, and interaction with the audience as a medium for Islamic learning (Faumi *et al.*, 2024). Other studies also use content analysis to evaluate Islamic Religious Education (PAI) and character education textbooks in terms of material aspects, gender bias, and worship content.

Through a deep understanding of content analysis techniques, it is expected that the quality and accuracy of research in communication, education, humanities, and other social sciences can be significantly improved. Ultimately, this study contributes not only to enriching the body of knowledge but also to providing a strong foundation for better professional practices in the future.

METHOD

This type of research is a literature review study, which is one form of library research (Salmaa, 2023), using a descriptive qualitative approach. Library research is a study that utilizes resources available in libraries and documents such as books, journal articles, research reports, written digital and online sources, databases, as well as other visual and audio materials to explore and analyze existing literature, data, and sources related to the research topic (Abdurrahman, 2024). The literature review is conducted to identify definitions, trends, approaches, objectives, and uses, as well as the stages or procedures of content analysis research in the fields of education, communication, language, socio-political studies, and others. A literature review is chosen because it allows researchers to systematically identify, evaluate, and synthesize previous research findings, thereby building a comprehensive understanding of the presented content analysis techniques. To support this study, the author uses more recent journal articles, books, research reports, as well as information or references from websites related to both primary and supporting data.

The data collection and analysis techniques are carried out based on the following methods: (1) Editing, which involves checking the completeness of the data, ensuring clarity of meaning, and the consistency of the data or references used; (2) Organizing, which refers to arranging data or references according to the relevant topics or frameworks; and (3) Finding, which involves analyzing the organized data based on established rules, theories, and methods (Salmaa, 2023). Alternatively, the process can be conducted using data induction steps, which include identifying or determining the topic, collecting sources of information or data, selecting relevant sources, and

analyzing and evaluating the data or literature collected as sources of information (Sari & Asmendri, 2020; Subagiya, 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Concept of Content Analysis Method

The content analysis method is one of the important research techniques in social sciences, language studies, and other fields. Content analysis presents the understanding that society is shaped or constructed through discourse, texts, and other forms of communication, so that understanding social phenomena cannot be achieved without first understanding how text or language operates (A. Asfar, 2019). Language operates not merely as a tool to convey messages, but as a symbolic system that constructs meaning, ideology, and power relations. Therefore, in the context of content analysis, understanding how language operates means tracing how texts or discourses convey meaning both implicitly and explicitly, as well as how linguistic structures reflect and reproduce certain social values. According to experts, content analysis in general is a method used to examine various characteristics in media (text, audio, visual, documents, etc.). This method discusses the content of information or messages as data in depth in any form. Data is treated as communication that is deliberately created and disseminated to be understood by the audience (Ahmad, n.d.). Content analysis is a methodological approach used to systematically and objectively examine communication content while minimizing bias, both quantitatively (number-based) and qualitatively. This method helps researchers identify patterns, themes, and meanings contained in various forms of media such as text, images, audio, and video.

Furthermore, Heriyanto (2018) states that content analysis can be used in qualitative research because it is highly suitable for analyzing messages or texts that often contain multiple meanings. These meanings are not singular but open to various interpretations depending on the reader and the context (Lestari & Satrio, 2019). Content analysis can be applied to data such as books or documents including newspapers, magazines, recordings, manuscripts, or content from YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, or films. In the context of social and humanities research, content analysis becomes an important tool for understanding symbolic representations, narratives, and communication structures implicitly embedded in documents or mass media. In practice, content analysis can be conducted quantitatively by focusing on counting the occurrence of certain elements such as words, phrases, or symbols, or qualitatively by interpreting the meaning and context of communication content (Asfar, 2019).

Berelson defines content analysis as a research technique used to identify specific characteristics of message content objectively, systematically, and quantitatively. He argues that content analysis focuses on the content itself rather than the intention behind the message or the audience's response. This limitation is based on three reasons: (1) low validity due to lack of direct data on intention and response, (2) low reliability because different coders may classify intentions differently, and (3) the possibility of circular reasoning when linking intention, effect, and content (Lestari & Satrio, 2019). On the other hand, Janice M. Morse (1991) states that in research, people can use several techniques, considering that research methodology is a tool or instrument used to facilitate understanding. Therefore, content analysis research can be implemented in both qualitative and quantitative research across many fields of study. The current methodological debate is not about whether one method is intrinsically better than another, but rather that combining methods is the best way to meet the objectives of a particular study.

Nevertheless, research methodology is a tool that helps facilitate understanding (Barbara Downe-Wamboldt RN, 1992). Likewise, the content analysis method being discussed. Krippendorff states that content analysis is a method used to produce replicable and valid inferences from data by considering the context of the content or message. Content analysis is not limited to specific types of content, whether written text, visual media, audio, or digital formats, making it highly relevant in the modern era of information and communication (Krippendorff, 2018).

2. Objectives and Urgency of the Content Analysis Method

Content analysis has its roots in long-standing scientific urgencies. This method was first used in political propaganda studies in the early 20th century, when Harold Lasswell analyzed mass media content to identify symbolic patterns formed within political messages during World War I, which later became known as "symbol coding." Symbol coding became an essential activity for systematically recording symbols or signs in messages so that they could be interpreted. At that time, Lasswell conducted his analysis using a quantitative approach as a tool to calculate the frequency of certain symbols and words appearing (Barbara Downe-Wamboldt RN, 1992). Content analysis or content analysis techniques had actually been used as early as 400 years ago during the era of Ancient Rome. This statement is based on the ideas of Aristotle regarding rhetoric, which marked one of the early indications of the application of content analysis in the rhetorical process of constructing messages (Eriyanto, 2015).

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Rhetoric can be understood as the art of public speaking and constructing arguments, which later evolved into various ways humans rely on symbols to influence audiences around them (Dhia *et al.*, 2024). The first practical application of content analysis, as traced historically, occurred around the 18th century in Sweden. At that time, an event caused controversy within an orthodox church group due to the circulation of a popular book among the public containing around 90 hymns titled “Song of Zion.” There were concerns that the book contained heretical elements or teachings that deviated from church doctrine. Scholars were then invited to examine the contents of the book. They were divided into two groups tasked with counting religious symbols in both the popular hymn book and the official hymn book, and then comparing them. The research results showed that both produced the same outcome, with no differences found (Eriyanto, 2015).

In the 19th century, content analysis developed significantly with the expansion of journalism studies and newspaper analysis, which became increasingly popular in United States. The rapid growth of journalism schools stimulated the need for empirical research on newspapers, and gradually more studies began to use content analysis techniques in press research. As a result, in this century, content analysis began to spread widely as a tool for analyzing electronic media such as radio and film. This was notably seen in studies on commercial films funded by The Payne Fund, which aimed to examine the effects of films on society and to classify film themes shown in cinemas (Eriyanto, 2015; Krippendorff, 2018).

The content analysis research method has various objectives depending on the approach, type of data, and research context used. Fundamentally, the purpose of content analysis, in line with its definition, is to identify, categorize, and interpret communication content systematically and objectively, including efforts to understand what is contained within it, whether in written, visual, or audio forms. Content analysis using a quantitative approach aims to calculate how often certain elements appear in texts, such as words, phrases, or themes, allowing researchers to obtain statistical results that can be empirically tested (Nugraha *et al.*, 2025; Sumarno, 2020; Ulfah *et al.*, 2022).

Meanwhile, the use of content analysis with a qualitative approach focuses more on the freedom to explore meaning, narrative composition, and social representations embedded within communication content. In this context, researchers focus on the process of how messages are formed, delivered, and received by audiences, while considering the influence of social and cultural factors. This approach allows researchers to uncover and understand values, ideologies, and perceptions that are not directly visible within the text or media being studied. In other words, the goal is to go beyond the literal meaning of a text or media (Nugraha *et al.*, 2025).

The objective of content analysis is to examine content in order to discover the “meaning behind the meaning,” often referred to as hidden ideologies and perceptions. For example, in film analysis, researchers not only examine the storyline but also analyze how the film represents power, gender, or social class, and other aspects that reflect ideology or perception. Furthermore, as explained by Krippendorff (2018), the main objective of content analysis is to draw valid and replicable conclusions from the collected data while considering the communication context in which the message is situated. This means that if other researchers use the same method, they should be able to achieve similar results, ensuring that findings are not subjective or random.

Another objective of content analysis is to identify recurring and significant communication patterns within a set of data. In mass media research, content analysis is used to identify news framing, media bias, and how media portray certain social groups. For example, in research conducted by Indra *et al.* on political humor messages on TikTok ahead of the 2024 election, content analysis was used to examine various forms of humor such as satire, parody, irony, and *parikena* found in the content. This method helps analyze how humor becomes an effective communication strategy for conveying criticism or political support, attracting public attention, especially among younger generations, and assessing the socio-political implications arising from the use of humor in social media. Thus, content analysis enables a comprehensive understanding of modern political communication and its impact in the digital media context (Indra *et al.*, 2024).

In the field of education, the objectives of content analysis include evaluating curriculum content, textbooks, and learning materials. Research conducted by Siti Khalijah and Zuliana (2024) analyzed the content of Islamic Religious Education materials in the Merdeka Curriculum to assess their alignment with new curriculum principles, such as learning flexibility and character development. The study also identified various learning challenges, such as low student interest, less engaging teaching methods, and suboptimal teacher competence. Additionally, analysis was conducted on core values contained in the material, such as *aqidah*, *akhlak*, *fiqh*, the Qur’an and Hadith, and the history of Islamic civilization, to evaluate their contribution to students’ spiritual, intellectual, and social development. Thus, content analysis functions not only as an evaluative tool but also as a foundation for improving and innovating more contextual and transformative learning materials (Khalijah & Zuliana, 2024).

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In the context of digital media and social media, content analysis aims to understand user behavior, communication trends, and the dynamics of online interaction. For example, research conducted by Anggi Aldila Safitri (2021) used quantitative content analysis to examine message characteristics on the Instagram account @netflixid and their impact on user engagement. By measuring three main aspects, namely content objectives, message orientation, and visual elements, the study found that only visual elements such as images, teasers, and film posters had a significant influence on user engagement. These findings confirm that in social media environments, visual strength and emotional appeal are key factors in building relationships between brands and audiences (Safitri, 2021). In the study by Khalijah and Zuliana (2024), it is stated that content analysis aims to analyze the content of Islamic Religious Education materials in the Merdeka Curriculum. The research theme is motivated by the many problems encountered in the teaching and learning process. This objective is descriptive and evaluative, aiming to determine the extent to which PAI materials in the Merdeka Curriculum align with: (1) Islamic values; (2) supporting holistic student development; and (3) promoting religious moderation.

Overall, the objectives of content analysis research techniques depend heavily on the focus and design of the study. However, in general, this method aims to: (1) identify and classify communication content systematically; (2) measure the frequency and distribution of communication elements; (3) interpret the meaning and context of the messages studied; (4) reveal social representations, ideologies, and values in communication; (5) develop new theories from empirical data; (6) evaluate educational, policy, and media content; and (7) understand digital communication dynamics and online behavior (Asfar, 2019; Rozali, Yuli, 2022; Sumarno, 2020).

Additionally, Krippendorff (2018), citing Berelson (1952), describes the broad objectives of content analysis as follows: “1) To describe trends in communication content, 2) To trace the development of scholarship; 3) To disclose international differences in communication content; 4) To compare media or levels of communication; 5) To audit communication content against objectives; 6) To construct and apply communication standards; 7) To aid in technical research operations (to code open-ended questions in survey interviews); 8) To expose propaganda techniques; 9) To measure the readability of communication materials, 10) To discover stylistic features; 11) To identify the intentions and other characteristics of the communicators; 12) To determine the psychological state of persons or groups; 13) To detect the existence of propaganda (primarily for legal purposes); 14) To secure political and military intelligence; 15) To reflect attitudes, interests, and values (cultural patterns) of population groups; and 16) To describe attitudinal and behavioral responses to communications.”

Based on its application, content analysis has flexible objectives and methods. With its flexibility and depth, content analysis becomes a highly useful method across various disciplines such as education, communication, sociology, humanities, political science, and others (Krippendorff, 2018). These objectives make content analysis not only descriptive but also interpretative, theoretical, and critical in understanding communication phenomena comprehensively. Research using content analysis in the field of education includes studies such as that of Siti Khadijah and Zuliana (2024) on Islamic Religious Education materials in the Merdeka Curriculum, Hidayat (2025) on textbook analysis, and Sumarno (2020) on language and literature learning. In cultural studies, content analysis is used to explore how films, advertisements, or literary works represent cultural values and symbols. In gender studies, this method is crucial for examining how media portray men and women, which can reinforce or challenge social constructions of gender roles (Tresia *et al.*, 2024). Research is also widely conducted in communication studies, both in printed and digital media, as well as in socio-political research themes.

In addition, content analysis plays an important role in evaluative research. For example, this method is used to measure the effectiveness of communication campaigns, social programs, or public policy interventions. By analyzing promotional materials, activity reports, or audience feedback, researchers can assess whether messages have been properly understood, whether desired behavioral changes have occurred, and the extent of the impact of such interventions. In this context, content analysis becomes a concrete and measurable tool to provide a comprehensive overview of program success, thereby supporting future decision-making (Krippendorff, 2018; Nikita, 2024; Rizqullah Nugraha *et al.*, 2023).

In qualitative research, content analysis is not merely related to numerical or quantitative aspects but extends to exploring experiences, perceptions, and implicit values within media content or messages. This analysis is conducted through a coding process in which researchers identify meaningful elements within the data and classify them into specific categories or themes. Through this process, researchers can easily identify significant patterns and construct in-depth interpretations of the phenomena being studied. Moreover, the flexibility of content analysis in handling various types of data and sources of information is one of its key advantages (Asfar, 2019). One advantage of content analysis is its unobtrusiveness, meaning that it allows researchers to examine data without influencing it. As a result, researchers can obtain information that is often difficult or even impossible to acquire through other

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methods such as interviews or direct observation. The information obtained tends to be more authentic and objective, making content analysis an adaptive and relevant method for addressing exploratory and evaluative research questions (Rozali, Yuli, 2022). In addition, content analysis is a research method with relatively easier and more flexible data collection and analysis processes (Methodology, 2025).

3. Procedure of Content Analysis Research Method

The flexibility and development of content analysis methods allow researchers to use them as powerful tools to explore deep and hidden meanings behind communication data. By examining how messages are formed, delivered, received, and evaluated, content analysis not only helps researchers understand what is explicitly stated in verbal, audio, visual, and multimedia or multilingual forms, but also reveals why and how these messages influence society. Content analysis operates on the principle that communication data, whether verbal, visual, or digital, contains patterns and meanings that can be analyzed systematically. Initially, this method was widely used in mass communication studies to analyze media content such as newspapers and television broadcasts, with the aim of identifying narrative patterns, news framing, and media bias that indirectly shape public perception. Through this approach, researchers can uncover how media selects words, constructs stories, and uses visuals to influence audience perspectives on political, social, and cultural issues.

The content analysis method has increasingly developed and expanded into various fields, contributing to the advancement and innovation of information and knowledge. According to Krippendorff (2018), the most important aspect of content analysis is its ability to reveal messages, meanings, ideologies, values, and power dynamics hidden within communication. The goal of content analysis is to produce valid and replicable inferences. This ensures that research findings are objective and can be tested again, rather than being merely subjective interpretations. By systematically examining elements of messages, from word choices to narrative structures, researchers can uncover hidden agendas that may not be consciously recognized by message creators or audiences. In other words, content analysis helps us understand how communication functions as a tool to spread, maintain, or challenge ideologies within society. Content analysis is a holistic and multifunctional research method. Its strength lies in its ability to go beyond surface meanings, uncover deeper layers of meaning, and connect communication with broader social, cultural, and power dynamics.

Klaus Krippendorff (2018) developed a framework for content analysis that does not treat text as merely a passive object for counting words or symbols mechanically. Instead, he emphasizes that text is a rich entity of meaning, consisting of messages, references, and social roles embedded in communication practices. In Krippendorff's perspective, there are two main worlds interacting in the content analysis process: the social world, referred to as "the many worlds of others," and the analytical world constructed by the researcher, called "context as conceived by content analysts." Text exists at the intersection of these two worlds. In the social world, text meaning is dynamic, depending on the cultural, social, and historical context in which it is used. Meaning is not fixed or independent, but diffused through social interactions and communicative practices. In analyzing it, researchers do not simply read text literally but must explore its social function and how it is interpreted by native speakers or the community that uses it. This process requires empirical validation, involving the testing of interpretations through external evidence to avoid speculative or subjective conclusions. This approach is strengthened through triangulation between text, social meaning, and relevant contextual conditions (Krippendorff, 2018).

In analyzing text or objects, researchers begin by formulating clear and focused research questions (Salmaa, 2023). According to Krippendorff (2018), these questions form the basis for determining the focus of analysis, developing coding categories, and selecting interpretation methods. Researchers must also consider contributing conditions, which are external factors influencing the production and consumption of text, such as ideological values, social policies, or political dynamics shaping communication contexts. The ultimate goal is to produce analytical answers that explain stable relationships between text, its meanings, and the surrounding social conditions, thereby revealing communication phenomena more comprehensively and deeply.

According to Krippendorff (2018), in obtaining meaning, content analysis should not stop at quantitative mapping of symbols or words. As a mediator, the researcher connects the social world with the analytical world through valid, reliable, and transparent interpretations. By building strong analytical constructions and drawing appropriate inferences based on data, content analysis can provide meaningful insights that not only explain the text but also its function in complex social communication. Therefore, there are two types of content analysis: conceptual analysis and relational analysis (Salmaa, 2023). The stages of implementing content analysis consist of several steps, which will be explained along with examples of their application in studies analyzing Islamic Religious Education

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materials, learning media, textbooks, and language and literature learning (Faumi *et al.*, 2024; Hidayat, 2025; Khalijah & Zuliana, 2024; Sumarno, 2020; Wijayat & Hernawati, 2025).

Based on various implementations, the steps of content analysis can be carried out as follows

a. Formulating the Analysis Objectives

The first and most crucial step is determining clear and specific research objectives. These objectives serve as a guide for the entire analysis process. Without well-defined objectives, research may lose focus and produce irrelevant findings. Researchers need to formulate key questions such as “What thematic patterns dominate this text?”, “How often does a concept appear?”, or “How are relationships between concepts formed?”. The clarity of objectives determines the type of data needed and whether a quantitative or qualitative approach is more appropriate.

b. Selecting Content for Analysis

The next step is selecting relevant topics or content. This content can include written texts, interview transcripts, visual media, or audio recordings. It is important to ensure that the selected content represents the phenomenon being studied and aligns with the research questions. Sampling techniques such as purposive sampling or random sampling can be used to ensure validity and reliability.

For example, in a study analyzing Islamic Religious Education textbooks, Khalijah and Zuliana (2024) selected content focusing on teaching materials within the Merdeka Curriculum. The unit of analysis included content structure and learning principles, covering aspects such as *aqidah*, Qur'an and Hadith, *fiqh*, morality, and Islamic civilization history.

c. Developing a Coding Scheme

This stage is the core of content analysis, where researchers create a framework for classifying data. Categories must be clearly defined, mutually exclusive, and well-structured to avoid confusion. Categories can be developed through

1. Inductive approach, where categories emerge naturally from the data after identifying patterns
2. Deductive approach, where categories are predetermined based on existing theories or literature

Research findings often reveal issues such as low student interest, ineffective teaching methods, insufficient teacher competence, and lack of student engagement in learning Islamic Religious Education.

d. Data Collection and Preparation

Before coding, researchers must collect and prepare data systematically. This includes transcribing interviews, gathering documents, or recording observations. Data must be complete and contextualized. Preparation involves cleaning and formatting data to facilitate analysis, especially when using software tools.

e. Coding Process

Coding involves labeling units of analysis such as words, sentences, paragraphs, or images according to categories. This can be done manually or using software like NVivo or Atlas.ti to improve efficiency and accuracy. Consistency is essential so that similar data is coded uniformly, ensuring reliability and replicability.

f. Data Analysis and Interpretation

After coding, researchers analyze and interpret findings by organizing categories and identifying patterns. The results are then used to answer research questions. Conclusions must be based on systematic and objective data analysis rather than subjective assumptions.

g. Drawing Conclusions

Interpretation involves assigning theoretical and contextual meaning to identified patterns and relationships. Conclusions must be based on empirical evidence and linked to relevant theoretical frameworks. They should remain objective, avoid unsupported speculation, and acknowledge limitations.

For example, Khalijah and Zuliana (2024) concluded that Islamic Religious Education materials in the Merdeka Curriculum align with the goals of developing students spiritually, intellectually, and socially, based on content structure and embedded Islamic values.

h. Validity and Reliability

To ensure research credibility, content analysis must undergo validity and reliability testing

1. Validity refers to how accurately categories represent theoretical concepts, improved through triangulation, expert validation, and pre-testing
2. Reliability ensures consistency and replicability, enhanced through coding guidelines, coder training, and inter-coder agreement

Although some studies may not explicitly address these aspects, validity can still be inferred from the use of credible academic sources.

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i. Reporting and Presenting Findings

The final stage involves presenting findings systematically in a scientific report, including background, methodology, results, interpretation, and conclusions. Supporting data such as quotes, tables, and charts help illustrate key findings. Reports should also discuss theoretical and practical implications and provide recommendations for future research. Dissemination can be done through seminars, conferences, or academic publications. Overall, content analysis is a widely used and continuously evolving research method. It not only describes communication content but also helps understand meaning, context, and impact across various fields such as communication, education, humanities, and social and political sciences. Its flexibility and analytical depth make it a valuable tool in both academic and practical applications.

CONCLUSION

The content analysis method is a systematic and objective approach to examining meanings and patterns that represent various forms of communication, including text, visual, and audio. In the context of the complex digital era, this method has become an important tool for understanding media dynamics, public discourse, and educational content. The purpose of this analysis, as defined, is to analyze the meaning of texts and messages in depth, explore the underlying meanings, examine them, and describe them through patterns and categories of meaning that provide broader and more comprehensive concepts or information.

Content analysis has long been used by scholars to explore and break down information and knowledge through media or messages, whether written, spoken, or digital. Therefore, this research provides significant benefits in enriching the body of knowledge. This method can be conducted both quantitatively and qualitatively, and it can be used as a data analysis technique in various fields of study such as Islamic Education, Religious Studies, Communication, Language and Literature, Social Sciences, Politics, and others. The stages of content analysis can be carried out through the following procedures: (1) determining the objectives of the analysis, (2) selecting the content to be analyzed, (3) developing a theoretical framework for categories, (4) data collection and preparation, (5) the coding process, (6) data analysis and interpretation, (7) drawing conclusions, (8) conducting validity and reliability checks, and (9) reporting and presenting the findings.

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CONCEPT AND PROCEDURE OF THE CONTENT ANALYSIS METHOD FOR EXPLORING INFORMATION IN THE FIELDS OF ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION, COMMUNICATION, SOCIAL SCIENCES, AND HUMANITIES

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